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**THE INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ROMANIAN AS A
FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH INTERCULTURAL ASPECT**

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The major goal of the present study is to highlight and to tight connection and independence between language and culture from both theoretical and practical perspectives, we focus on the reciprocal influence and impact on teaching Romanian language to foreign students. Famous researchers have wisely noted the sine-qua non relation of society, culture and language evinced in the process of communication, at large, and most notably in translation and language learning, which are complex processes requiring a thorough and conscious immersion in the context of the language.

One of the goals for learners who study a foreign language is to communicate with the target language users, either native target language speakers or those who use it as a second or foreign language. Evidences from researches of both spoken and written discourses demonstrated that linguistics phenomena are related to their society and culture. Foreign culture learning can contribute to the success in language because success in language learning is conditional upon the acquisition of cultural knowledge and language learners acquire cultural background knowledge in order to communicate, and to increase their comprehension in the target language. The teachers in this case will use different innovative and interactive methods to teach both the culture and the language itself. At our department, weekly the teachers make a special lesson about culture of Republic of Moldova and in general about Romanian culture. This kind of lessons gives the students the possibility to discover the more interesting way of

learning Romanian. Audio exercises, video helps us, teachers to show the beauty of our culture.

Teaching foreign languages at the university with the use of interactive methods are aimed at solving several problems: communicative-cognitive, which teaches communication skills; concrete-cognitive, which considers a specific educational situation; socially oriented, which shapes and develops adequate socialization of a person beyond the educational situation. Among the interactive methods of teaching, we would like to highlight some of the most effective ones. Such methods of teaching are discussion, collective situation analysis (case-study method) and role-playing. The role - playing like between patient and doctor helps students to achieve a good competence of communication in Romanian language.